

saponin and was hydrolysed with 6% methanolic HCl. The aglycone was separated and identified as mollugogenol A (vide *supra*). The sugars in the hydrolysate were identified as rhamnose and glucose. TLC monitored hydrolysis of the saponin revealed the sugar sequence in it as rhamnose→glucose→aglycone. 20.1 mg of the saponin was hydrolysed with 7% H₂SO₄ in 5 ml MeOH in a sealed tube and the sapogenin and the sugars were estimated¹⁷. Mollugogenol A was found to be 52.61% (required 52.89%) and the sugars 46.83% (required 47.10%). This showed that glucose and rhamnose were present in 1 : 1 ratio. It is well known that natural triterpenoid glycosides are usually C3-O-glycoside¹⁸. Hence the disaccharide chain was linked to mollugogenol A at position 3 through glucose. Further, furanose configuration for glucose is very uncommon among natural glycosides. It was therefore assumed that glucose unit was in pyranose form leaving 4-OH group free for glycosidic linkage with the terminal rhamnose unit, which also existed in pyranose form in natural glycosides. Furthermore, it is a general observation that D-sugars occur with β-glycosidic linkages and L-sugars with α-glycosidic linkages¹⁹. Based on above facts the structure of the above compound i.e. saponin of mollugogenol A may be represented as α-L-rhamnopyranosyl(1→4)-β-D-glycopyranosyl(1→3)-mollugogenol A (1).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Professor K. D. Banerji, Professor of Chemistry, Bhagalpur University for facilities and to the U.G.C., New Delhi for financial assistance to one of them (P.K.G.).

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2'-Mercapto Maleianilic Acid as a New Gravimetric Reagent for the Determination and Separation of Zirconium(IV) and Thorium(IV)

NEPAL SINGH*, POONAM AGRAWAL
and
VINITA GUPTA

Department of Chemistry, Hindu College, Moradabad
*Manuscript received 11 May 1982, revised 27 April 1983,
accepted 1 September 1983*

ORGANIC acids and their derivatives have been investigated by several workers for the estimation of zirconium¹⁻⁶ and thorium⁷⁻¹¹. In continuation of our previous work^{1,2}, we report the use of 2'-mercapto maleianilic acid as a new gravimetric reagent for the determination of Zr(IV) and Th(IV) and their separation from binary mixture by using a mixture of citrate and tartrate (1 : 1 molar ratio) as masking agent for zirconium(IV) ion. Ammonium nitrate has been used as a coagulating agent for better crystallization.

Experimental

2'-Mercapto maleianilic acid has been prepared by condensing purified maleic anhydride and *o*-amino thiophenol. The purity of the compound was confirmed by elemental analysis. (Found : C, 53.9 ; H, 4.75 ; N, 5.67. Calcd. : C, 53.94 ; H, 4.16 ; N, 5.2%). The condensation takes place according to the following way :

Sodium salt of the acid was prepared by dissolving the required amount of the reagent in a minimum

* Author for correspondence : 42, Malviya Nagar, Moradabad-244 001.

volume of 0.1 M NaOH solution, diluted with distilled water and its pH (6.5-6.8) was adjusted with 0.01 M acetic acid.

Stock solutions of zirconium and thorium were prepared by the usual procedure^{1,3} from the requisite amount of ZrOCl₂·8H₂O and Th(NO₃)₄·5H₂O (E. Merck) in distilled water. Metal contents of the solutions were determined gravimetrically^{1,4}.

Determination of Zr(IV) :

Aliquots of the stock solution of Zr(IV) (containing 2.73-27.35 mg) were diluted to about 100 ml with distilled water and heated to 40-50° on a water bath and 150 mg of NH₄NO₃ added. The pH of the mixture was adjusted at 5.5 to 6.8 by adding acetate buffer. 1% solution (w/v) of the reagent (2'-MMA) was then added with constant stirring. A white precipitate gradually separated out which was digested on water-bath (60-75°) for about 30 min. The precipitate was filtered in a sintered glass crucible (G-4) and washed several times with distilled water. It was dried at 130-135° and weighed as [Zr(C₁₀H₇NO₃S)O(H₂O)]₂. (Found : C, 29.2 ; H, 3.5 ; N, 3.8. Calcd. : C, 34.3 ; H, 3.62 ; N, 4.02%). The conversion factor from complex to metal is 0.2632. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF Zr(IV) AS MERCAPTO ANILIC ACID COMPLEX

Sl. No.	Zr(IV) taken mg	Complex obtained mg	Zr(IV) found mg	% error
1.	2.73	10.34	2.721	-0.32
2.	3.64	13.82	3.648	+0.21
3.	9.11	34.48	9.075	-0.38
4.	13.67	51.82	13.63	-0.29
5.	18.23	69.08	18.18	-0.27
6.	27.35	103.60	27.26	-0.34

The TGA curve indicates a continuous loss in weight upto 130° owing to the elimination of loosely held water in complex lattice. Due to the stability of the complex at 130-150°, the curve remains horizontal. The coordinated water molecules in the complex are eliminated at 180-220° through a slow decomposition (% loss : Found : 5.56 ; Calcd. 5.19). The fast decomposition of the residue occurs at 260-380° with a plateau at 240-260°, followed by slow decomposition continuing upto 480°. Thereafter the curve becomes horizontal due to complete oxidation of the residue to ZrO₂. (% loss : Found : 68.8 ; Calcd. 74.0). The mode of decomposition can be represented as :

Determination of Th(IV) :

A known volume of the stock solution of Th(IV) (containing 6.95-46.39 mg) was taken in a 400 ml

beaker, diluted to 100 ml with distilled water and heated on a water bath at 40-60° and 200 mg of NH₄NO₃ added. The pH of the solution was adjusted at 5.5-7.0 by adding acetate buffer. The solution of the reagent (2'-MMA) (1.0% w/v) was added with constant stirring. A white precipitate gradually separated out which was digested on water bath for about 30 min. It was allowed to cool and then filtered in a sintered crucible (G-4). The precipitate was repeatedly washed with water to remove all other ions, dried at 130-135° and weighed as [Th(C₁₀H₇NO₃S)(OH)₂(H₂O)]₂. (Found : C, 30.55 ; H, 2.84 ; N, 2.0. Calcd. C, 26.60 ; H, 2.76 ; N, 1.86%). The conversion factor from complex to metal is 0.4592. The results of estimations are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF Th(IV) AS COMPLEX

Sl. No.	Th(IV) taken mg	Complex obtained mg	Th(IV) found mg	% error
1.	6.95	15.10	6.93	-0.37
2.	9.27	20.14	9.24	-0.32
3.	11.59	25.26	11.60	+0.08
4.	23.18	50.91	23.12	-0.24
5.	46.39	101.2	46.47	+0.17

TGA curve indicates that all the loosely held water in lattice is completely eliminated around 130°, causing a small loss in weight. Thereafter the weight of the complex remains constant due to the thermal stability of the compound. Further loss in weight starts at 160° and continues upto 220°, which is due to the elimination of coordinated water and a water molecule from the hydroxy groups acting as a bridge between two thorium atoms (% loss : Found : 5.64 ; Calcd. 5.32). A fast decomposition of the complex starts at 220° and continues upto 380° and is followed by slow decomposition upto 660° at which it is completely oxidised to thoria (% loss : Found : 49.5 ; Calcd. 48.0). The mode of decomposition can be represented as

Effect of foreign ions :

To study the influence of foreign ions on the estimation of zirconium(IV) and thorium(IV), a definite amount of foreign ion was added prior to the ligand (2'-MMA) solution [18.23 mg Zr(IV)/100 ml and 9.278 mg Th(IV)/100 ml]. The estimation was carried out according to the procedure described above. It is observed that there is no interference of Cu(II), Cd(II), Zn(II), Ni(II), Hg(II), Sn(II), Mg(II), Pr(III), Sm(III), La(III), Cr(III), Mn(II), Ca(II) and Sr(II) because of their reluctance to

TABLE 3—SEPARATION AND DETERMINATION OF Zr(IV) AND Th(IV) FROM THEIR BINARY MIXTURE

Sl. No.	Metal ion taken (mg)		Complex obtained (mg)		Metal ions found (mg)		% error	
	Zr(IV)	Th(IV)	Zr(IV)	Th(IV)	Zr(IV)	Th(IV)	Zr(IV)	Th(IV)
1.	9.11	9.27	34.48	20.14	9.06	9.248	-0.54	0.32
2.	13.67	11.59	51.76	25.28	13.62	11.60	-0.36	+0.08
3.	18.23	23.18	69.02	50.98	18.62	23.13	-0.38	-0.21
4.	27.35	46.39	104.00	100.8	27.37	46.28	+0.07	-0.25
5.	45.58	69.59	173.0	151.2	45.42	69.43	-0.35	-0.32
6.	54.70	92.78	208.0	202.2	54.74	92.85	+0.07	+0.75

form complex with the reagent at pH 5.5-7.0. The ions NO_2^- , NO_3^- , Cl^- , Br^- , CNS^- , $\text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{O}_2^-$, SO_4^{2-} , BO_3^{3-} and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ also do not interfere in the determination. Interference due to Ag(I), Tl(I), Fe(II) and Fe(III) was avoided by adding an appropriate quantity of a mixture of tartrate and EDTA (1 : 1 molar ratio).

Determination and separation of zirconium and thorium in their binary mixture by using 2'-mercapto maleianilic acid :

When Zr(IV) and Th(IV) ions were present together in a solution, thorium was precipitated first as $[\text{Th}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{NO}_3\text{S})(\text{OH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2$ in presence of a mixture of citrate and tartrate. Thereafter Zr(IV) ions were demasked with conc. HNO_3 and determined as $[\text{Zr}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{NO}_3\text{S})\text{O}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2$.

Procedure :

The mixture containing known amounts of Zr(IV) and Th(IV) was taken in a 500 ml beaker and diluted to 100 ml with distilled water. An appropriate quantity of the masking agent, citrate and tartrate mixture (1 : 1 molar ratio), and 100-200 mg NH_4NO_3 as coagulating agent were added. The solution was then heated gently and its pH adjusted to 5.5-6.8 by acetate buffer. 1% aqueous solution (w/v) of the reagent was added gradually with constant stirring till the precipitation was complete. The white precipitate of thorium complex was digested on a water bath for 30 min. The precipitate was filtered in a sintered crucible (G-4), washed several times with water, dried at 130-135° and weighed.

The filtrate, containing zirconium was concentrated to 25% of the total volume, treated with appropriate quantity of conc. HNO_3 (twice the metal ion taken) and evaporated almost to dryness. The syrup was diluted with 10 ml water and again dried by evaporation. The residue was diluted with 100 ml distilled water and any adhering HNO_3 was just neutralised by sodium bicarbonate. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 5.5-6.8 by acetate buffer and the Zr(IV) complex precipitated and determined as described earlier. The results of the estimations are given in Table 3.

Discussion

The sensitivity of the organic acid was found to be 6.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 6.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for zirconium and thorium ions, respectively. The digestion of the precipitate at higher temperature (around 70°) does not affect the results of determination. The drying range of precipitate is also wide. The complexes are stable upto 150°. Thermal behaviour of the complexes supports 1 : 1 metal ligand ratio. It has also been observed that the zirconium complex is more stable than the thorium complex. The results obtained indicate that 2'-mercapto maleianilic acid is a promising gravimetric reagent for the estimation of Zr(IV) and Th(IV) in micro and semi-micro quantities.

Acknowledgement

The authors record their sincere thanks to Dr. R. N. Gupta, Principal, Hindu College, Moradabad for facilities.

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